

A Code Smell Refactoring Approach using GNNs

HanYu Zhang^a, Tomoji Kishi^a

^a*Department of Industrial and Management Systems Engineering, Waseda University*

bankzhy@akane.waseda.jp

Abstract

Code smell is a great challenge in software refactoring, which indicates latent design or implementation flaws that may degrade the software maintainability and evolution. Over the past decades, a variety of refactoring approaches have been proposed, which can be broadly classified into metrics-based, rule-based, and machine learning-based approaches. Recent years, deep learning-based approaches have also attracted widespread attention. However, existing techniques exhibit various limitations. Metrics- and rule-based approaches rely heavily on manually defined heuristics and thresholds, whereas deep learning-based approaches are often constrained by dataset availability and model design. In this study, we proposed a graph-based deep learning approach for code smell refactoring. Specifically, we designed two types of input graphs (class-level and method-level) and employed both graph classification and node classification tasks to address the refactoring of three representative code smells: long method, large class, and feature envy. In our experiment, we propose a semi-automated dataset generation approach that could generate a large-scale dataset with minimal manual effort. We implemented the proposed approach with three classical GNN (graph neural network) architectures: GCN, GraphSAGE, and GAT, and evaluated its performance against both traditional and state-of-the-art deep learning approaches. The results demonstrate that proposed approach achieves superior refactoring performance.

Keywords: code smell, long method, large class, feature envy, deep learning, graph neural network

1 Introduction

Software Refactoring has been playing an important role in software lifecycle helps to improve the maintainability and readability of the software. It refers to optimizing the software internal structure without changing its external behavior. During the software refactoring process, Code Smell has always been an important topic. This term was coined by Kent Beck and further explained by Fowler in 1999 [1]. They set out 22 typical code smells and described how to recognize them, such as long method, large class, feature envy. etc. Since then, code smell has become a popular topic in software engineering, attracting continuous attention from both academia and industry.

Over the past decades, numerous approaches for code smell refactoring have been proposed. According to surveys conducted by AbuHassan [2] and Sharma [3], nearly 100 types of code smells have been examined in the research community, with long method, large class, and feature envy being the most frequently studied. To address such more code smells, variety of refactoring techniques have also been proposed, which can be broadly categorized into metrics-based, rule-based, graph-based, and machine learning-based approaches.

Metric-based and rule-based approaches have long been the traditional and effective techniques for code smell refactoring. For example, Lanza [4] proposed more than 20 metrics and corresponding formulas to identify over six types of code smells. The well-known refactoring

tool JDeodorant [5] [6] [7] also relies on a large set of rules to identify code smells. These traditional approaches provide a useful basis for code smell refactoring. However, their effectiveness critically depends on how to define the optimal metrics or thresholds, which often require domain experts. Such reliance on human-designed heuristics substantially affects the accuracy and consistency of code smell refactoring.

To address the limitations of the above approaches, machine learning-based approaches become popular in the field of code smell refactoring. For instance, Fontana [9] applied 16 machine learning algorithms to detect code smells and conducted a comprehensive analysis. Furthermore, clustering techniques have also received considerable attention for identifying refactoring opportunities. For example, both the well-known tool JDeodorant and the approach proposed by Akash [21] employed the hierarchical agglomerative clustering (HAC) algorithm to identify opportunities for class extraction.

Compared with the above statistical machine learning-based approaches, deep learning approaches could often achieve better performance when large-scale data is available. Liu et al. [14] proposed a deep learning-based code smell detection approach which used software metrics as input features. To obtain substantial number of training samples, they introduced an automatic dataset generation approach called *smell introduction*, which deliberately injects undesired refactorings to degrade software quality and create labeled datasets. While this approach effectively demonstrated the applicability of deep learning to code smell detection, its performance was limited by the simplicity of the neural network architecture and the quality of the automatic generated data. Furthermore, no existing work has applied deep learning to identify refactoring opportunities. These gaps highlight the need for further research into more advanced deep learning architectures and datasets.

Graph neural network (GNN) [12][13] as an important division of deep learning which could directly apply neural network to graphs to capture interdependencies between nodes through message passing [22]. In this study, we investigate whether integrating GNNs with code smell refactoring could achieve improved performance. Specifically, we designed input graphs at two representation levels (class-level and method-level), and utilized several software metrics as node features. During the training process, graph classification is employed for code smell detection, while node classification is used to identify refactoring opportunities. To ensure sufficient data samples, we introduced a semi-automatic dataset generation approach to produce a large amount of high-quality data samples. We applied the proposed refactoring approach in three typical code smells: long method, large class and feature envy. In our experiment, we evaluated the proposed approach on three GNN model architecture: GCN [23], GraphSage [24], and GAT [25] to compare the results with the existing refactoring approaches. The experiment results proved that our approach could achieve better performance in code smell refactoring.

This study is a further extension of our previous works [10] [11], with improvements mainly reflected in two aspects. First, we extended the proposed GNN-based refactoring approach to support both code smell detection and refactoring opportunity identification, while also broadening its generalizability to more types of code smells. Second, we build a large-scale dataset using the upgraded semi-automated dataset generation approach and evaluate the proposed approach under more realistic and large-scale experimental settings. The details are listed as follows.

- Compared with our previous work [10][11], which focused only on detecting specific types of code smells, we extended the application of GNNs beyond code smell detection to the identification of refactoring opportunities from smell software entities. Moreover, in addition to long method and large class, we further applied the proposed approach to feature envy, thereby demonstrating its generalizability.
- Compared to our previous study [10][11], which evaluated the proposed approach on

a small, pre-constructed dataset, this work further improved the proposed semi-automatic dataset generation approach and constructed a large-scale dataset, which is publicly available at https://github.com/Bankzhy/GCSM_Dataset.git. Based on this dataset, we conducted extensive evaluation experiments with real-world open-source projects, thereby further proving the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews related studies on code smell refactoring, with a focus on three representative smells: long method, large class, and feature envy. Section 3 introduces the proposed semi-automated dataset generation approach. Section 4 describes the graph construction process at both the class and method levels. Section 5 presents the refactoring approach using GNNs with three representative code smells. Section 6 reports the experimental evaluation of the proposed approach. Section 7 discusses potential factors influencing the performance of our approach. Finally, Section 8 will conclude this paper.

2 Related Work

Since code smell was introduced by Fowler in 1999, many kinds of code smell refactoring approaches have been proposed. In this section, we introduce several representative approaches to code smell refactoring, with a primary focus on the three most widely studied code smells: long method, large class, and feature envy. The related studies are presented and discussed according to the underlying techniques employed.

From the history of code smell refactoring, metric-based approaches have been the dominant techniques. In the study by Lanza [4], they introduced a code smell detection approach with metrics and formulas. For long method detection, they utilized Eq. (1) to make smell detection with metrics lines of code (LOC), McCabe’s Cyclomatic Complexity (CYCLO), maximum nesting level (MAXNESTING), and number of accessed variables (NOAV). For large class detection, Eq. (2) was applied, utilizing metrics including: Access to foreign data (ATFD), weighted methods per class (WMC), and tight class cohesion (TCC). For feature envy detection, Eq. (3) was used, based on metrics ATFD, locality of attribute accesses (LAA), and foreign data providers (FDP). The corresponding thresholds (FEW, VERY HIGH, ONE THIRD, HIGH, SEVERAL, MANY) in these formulas were predefined by the specialist.

$$LOC > \frac{HIGH(Class)}{2} \wedge CYCLO > HIGH \wedge MAXNESTING > SEVERAL \wedge NOAV > MANY \quad (1)$$

$$ATFD > FEW \wedge WMC > VERY HIGH \wedge TCC < ONE THIRD \quad (2)$$

$$ATFD > FEW \wedge LAA < ONE THIRD \wedge FDP \leq FEW \quad (3)$$

JDeodorant [17] is a well-known refactoring tool for the Java language. It integrates metrics, rules, and machine learning techniques to detect code smells and identify refactoring opportunities. The tool primarily addresses four types of code smells: long method, large class, feature envy, and duplicated code. In the case of long method refactoring, the tool identifies two typical extract method opportunities: *complete computation* and *object state slice*. The first one refers to all statements that modify a single variable or parameter, while the second one denotes all statements that affect the same object. To achieve this, JDeodorant employs the Program Dependence Graph (PDG) [18] to perform block-based slicing on the original method and determine whether code segments could be safely extracted. In addition, a set of rules is applied to filter out refactoring opportunities that may alter the system’s external behavior. Once the valid opportunities are identified, the tool generates a candidate list and recommends it to developers.

For large class refactoring, JDeodorant first computes entity sets for each class member (attributes and methods). The Jaccard distance between entities is then calculated, and a HAC

algorithm is applied to identify extract class candidates. Rules are further defined to eliminate invalid candidates. The remaining valid candidates are regarded as the refactoring recommendations.

For feature envy detection, beyond member-level entity sets, the tool also computes entity sets at the class level. Rules are again defined to guide the formation of these sets. Subsequently, the Jaccard distance between methods and classes is computed to establish the preconditions for move method refactoring.

The above traditional approaches indeed provide useful means for addressing code smell refactoring. However, the major limitation lies in the strong dependence on manually designed metric formulas or rules, which require the involvement of software specialists. As a result, the effectiveness of refactoring highly depends on the human design. Furthermore, purely metrics-based approaches are generally limited to code smell detection, as they are unable to directly suggest refactoring opportunities. Usually, metrics-based approaches have often been combined with other techniques to support code smell refactoring in practical tools.

To overcome the above limitations, machine learning approaches have gained increasing popularity in recent studies. For instance, Fontana [9] conducted a comprehensive study by evaluating 16 different machine learning algorithms across four types of code smells (data class, large class, feature envy, and long method) on 74 software systems, comprising 1,986 manually validated code smell samples. Their experimental results demonstrated that applying machine learning to code smell detection could achieve high accuracy (exceeding 96%). Among the evaluated models, J48 achieved the best performance for long method and feature envy, whereas Naïve Bayes performed best for large class.

Deep learning, as a prominent research topic in recent years, has also been applied to code smell refactoring. In the study by Liu [14], software metrics were used as input features to the deep neural network to detect four types of code smells: feature envy, long method, large class, and misplaced class. To obtain a substantial number of training samples for deep learning, they introduced an automatic dataset generation approach called *smell-introducing refactoring*, which deliberately performs undesired refactorings that degrade software quality. For example, to generate large class data sample, several high-quality open-source projects were selected as data sources, and all classes were iterated to identify class pairs suitable for merging; the resulting merged class was treated as a positive sample, whereas the original classes were considered negative samples.

Despite its effectiveness, this approach also has limitations. First, as noted by the authors, the quality of the automatically generated dataset cannot be fully guaranteed, since it is difficult to ensure that all classes in open-source projects are well-designed, and not all merged classes necessarily exhibit the characteristics of a true large class. Second, the network architecture employed was relatively simple, and the input data relied heavily on pre-defined software metrics, which may limit the model's ability to capture complex structural relationships in code fragment.

In addition, numerous studies have also been proposed that focus on single code smell refactoring. For example, Shahidi [8] combined metrics and graph-based techniques for long method refactoring. Akash [21] applied similarity matrix and clustering techniques for large class refactoring. Since our study focuses on developing a generalizable approach for code smell refactoring. Therefore, we do not further discuss these single-smell approaches in detail.

According to the above studies, we could make conclusions as follows. First, traditional metrics- and rule-based approaches have played a fundamental role in code smell refactoring. However, these approaches exhibit notable limitations, as their performance heavily depends on expert-defined rules and thresholds. In contrast, machine learning-based approaches, particularly those leveraging deep learning, have emerged as a prominent research direction in

recent years. Nevertheless, these approaches continue to face significant challenges related to dataset quality and model design. In terms of applicability, metrics-based approaches are generally limited to code smell detection and typically need to be combined with other techniques to identify refactoring opportunities. For machine learning-based approaches, although several clustering-based approaches have been proposed to detect refactoring opportunities, most studies still primarily focus on detection tasks. Particularly for deep learning, despite its promising potential in code smell refactoring, current applications are most remain confined to code smell detection. Further studies are expected to achieve more comprehensive and effective refactoring performance.

In this paper, we propose a code smell refactoring approach based on GNNs. First, we extend the semi-automated dataset generation approach from our previous studies [10] [11] to create a dataset comprising over 17,000 positive samples for three widely studied code smells: long method, large class, and feature envy. Next, we construct input graphs at two levels: class-level and method-level and employ both graph classification and node classification tasks to perform code smell detection and identify refactoring opportunities. Finally, we evaluate our approach using three classical GNN architectures and compare the results with representative existing approaches. Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed approach achieved superior performance.

3 Dataset

In this section, we describe the semi-automated dataset generation approach. An overview of the approach is provided in Section 3.1, followed by a detailed explanation of each step in Sections 3.2 through 3.4.

3.1 Overview

To obtain a substantial number of high-quality data samples for deep learning, we propose a novel semi-automated dataset generation approach. The overall workflow of our approach is illustrated in Figure 1. Prior to dataset generation, several open-source projects are collected to construct a code corpus. In the first step, smelly software entities are intentionally created from the code corpus. Subsequently, a set of rules is applied to organize both the automatically generated samples and the original code corpus samples into two groups: A_Group and M_Group. Samples in A_Group are directly included in the final dataset, whereas samples in M_Group undergo manual verification by developers before integration. This manual checking process is facilitated by an annotation tool developed in this study. The details of each step are presented in the following subsections.

FIGURE 1 The overview of dataset generation

3.2 Data Sample Automatic Generation-Step.1

Deep learning models require a large number of training samples, yet smelly code samples are often scarce in open-source projects. Traditional manual approaches are therefore insufficient to address this challenge. To overcome this limitation, it is necessary to generate positive data samples automatically. In our approach, smelly software entities are first generated automatically from the code corpus according to predefined rules. The generation rules for each type of code smell are outlined as follows.

For long method, we identify three patterns of method invocation between methods and apply method merging accordingly. The first pattern occurs when a method is directly invoked as a statement. The second pattern arises when a variable within a statement is assigned the return value of another method. The third pattern involves cases where a method is invoked within an expression inside a statement. Once these method-merge opportunities are identified, we perform the merging operation and subsequently resolve any errors introduced during the process.

For example, the code in Figure 2 represents a program that sorts input numbers and prints them when their sum exceeds 10. In Pattern 1, the method *print_ary* is invoked at line S7 of the *main* method. In this case, the two methods exhibit a caller–callee relationship and can be merged by copying all statements from the callee method *print_ary* into the caller method *main*. The parameter *a* in *print_ary* is replaced with the corresponding variable *result* after the merge. Methods under Patterns 2 and 3 could be merged in a similar way to generate positive data samples. Further explanation could be found in our previous study [10].

FIGURE 2 Long method data sample generation

For large class, we designed two patterns of merging opportunities that can be automatically identified based on the three refactoring strategies for large classes introduced by Fowler [2]: *Extract Class*, *Extract Superclass*, and *Replace Type Code with Subclasses*. The two patterns are described as follows.

The first pattern involves classes with an inheritance relationship, where the parent class can be merged into the child class. For example, in Pattern 1 of Figure 3, the parent class *Product* can be merged into the child class *Book* by copying all methods and fields into the child class. The second pattern involves classes with a usage relationship, where one class is used as a field in another. As illustrated in Figure 3, the class *Cart* is used as a field within the class

User. In this case, the two classes can be merged by copying all fields and methods from *Cart* into *User*. Further explanation could be found in our previous study [11].

FIGURE 3 Large class data sample generation

For feature envy, we generate data samples by identifying related classes for each method according to three pattern rules and attempting to move the method to the related class. The rules for identifying related classes are illustrated in Figure 4.

FIGURE 4 Feature envy data sample generation

In the first pattern, we determine whether the class of the target method has a parent class. If so, we examine whether any unique fields of the current class are accessed by the target method. If no such fields are used, the method is considered a candidate for relocation to the parent class. In the second pattern, we identify related classes based on property usage. For example, in Figure 4, the method *discount* accesses the property *price* in the *Book* class. Since *price* is defined in the *Price* class, the method *discount* can be relocated from *Book* to *Price*. In the third pattern, related classes are inferred from the parameter list of the target method. For instance, in Figure 4, *campaign* is a parameter of the target method, and thus the class *Campaign* is regarded as a related class. In this case, the method *discount* can be moved to the *Campaign* class.

It should be noted that related classes are restricted to those defined within the project itself; generic language classes or classes defined in external APIs are excluded. If the method

relocation succeeds, the target method, along with its original class and target class, is recorded as a feature envy data sample. The reconstruction of methods and target classes differs across patterns. For example, in Pattern 2, the original class *Book* must be added as a field to the target class *Price*, and the invocation relationships in the relocated method must be updated accordingly. In Pattern 3, the parameters of the target method are replaced with references to the source class, and the invocation relationships are likewise modified.

3.3 Data Sample Grouping-Step.2

To efficiently obtain sufficient high-quality data samples, it is necessary to reduce the workload of human labeling as much as possible. Thus, we must determine which software entities have a higher possibility (or lower possibility) of being smelly, so that we can focus human effort on the ambiguous data samples. To achieve this, we designed several software metrics and rules for each code smell to group the data samples into two groups: *A_Group* and *M_Group*. The data samples in the *A_Group* will be directly applied to the final dataset, whereas the data samples in the *M_Group* are included after manual verification.

Table 1 Possibility range for long method dataset

	LOC Range	Description
PR1	0 to $MinTv$	The target method has low possibility of being long method
PR2	$MinTv$ to $MaxTv$	The target method has the possibility of being long method
PR3	More than $MaxTv$	The target method has great possibility of being long method

For long method, we used the LOC as the baseline metric and set up three possibility ranges, as shown in Table 1. Each possibility-range represents the different possibility that the method inside it could be considered as long method. The threshold values were set to $MaxTv = 30$ and $MinTv = 15$. The possibility-range settings are then used to partition the data samples into two groups, *A_Group* and *M_Group*, according to the rules specified in Table 2. The detail of this process is explained in our previous study [10].

Table 2 Grouping rules for long method dataset

Group	Rules
<i>A_Group</i>	1. The merged method with the LOC in PR3(>30) 2. The original method with the negative checked result by Advisor and the LOC in PR1(<15)
<i>M_Group</i>	1. The original method which LOC in PR3(>30) 2. The merged method with the LOC in PR2(15 to 30) 3. The original method with the negative checked result by Advisor and the LOC in PR2(15 to 30)

For large class, three baseline metrics were employed: LOC, *Number of Methods* (NOM), and *Number of Attributes* (NOA) to define three possibility-ranges, as shown in Table 3. Each possibility-range represents a different possibility that a class can be classified as a large class.

Table 3 Possibility range for large class dataset

	Metrics	Description
PR1	$LOC > MaxTv_{LOC} \ \&\& \ NOM > MaxTv_{NOM} \ \&\& \ NOA > MaxTv_{NOA}$	The class has great possibility to be a large class.
PR2	$LOC < MinTv_{LOC} \ \&\& \ NOM < MinTv_{NOM} \ \&\& \ NOA < MinTv_{NOA}$	The class has less possibility to be a large class.
PR3	other	The class has possibility to be a large class.

The values of $MaxTv$ and $MinTv$ for the large class depend on both the target programming language and the characteristics of the projects included in the code corpus. Therefore, it is

necessary to examine the specifications of the target language or collect statistical information on the relevant metrics within the corpus before determining appropriate threshold values. In this study, we adopted the *MaxTv* and *MinTv* values presented in Table 4. Subsequently, the data samples were divided into two groups, *A_Group* and *M_Group*, according to the rules summarized in Table 5. The detail of this process is explained in our previous study [11].

Table 4 The value of MaxTV and MinTv in large class

Group	NOA	NOM	LOC
MaxTv	10	10	130
MinTv	5	7	70

Table 5 Grouping rules for large class dataset

Group	Rules
M_group	1.The merged class in PR3 2.The original class in PR3 3.The original class in PR1
A_Group	1.The merged class in PR1 2.The original class in PR2

For feature envy, we employed a custom metric, *Number of Foreign Data Invocation (NFDI)*, as the baseline metric to define the possibility-ranges as shown in Table 6. The *NFDI* was inspired by the *ATFD* proposed by Lanza [4]. Specifically, *NFDI* measures the frequency with which attributes or methods from external classes are invoked within a given target method.

Table 6 Possibility range for feature envy dataset

	NGDI Range	Description
PR1	0 to MinTv	The target method has a low possibility of being feature envy.
PR2	MinTv to MaxTv	The target method has the possibility of being long feature envy.
PR3	More than MaxTv	The target method has great possibility of being feature envy.

In our approach, the values of *MaxTv* and *MinTv* were also determined based on a survey of code corpus data samples. We observed that methods affected by feature envy typically exhibit an *NFDI* between 2 and 5, whereas normal methods generally fall within the range of 0 to 5. Consequently, we set *MaxTv* to 5 and *MinTv* to 2. Using these thresholds, the possibility ranges were applied to divide the data samples according to the rules presented in Table 7.

Table 7 Grouping rules for feature envy dataset

Group	Rules
M_group	1.The moved method in PR2 2.The original method in PR2 3.The original method in PR3
A_Group	1.The moved method in PR3 2.The original method in PR1

3.4 Manually Checking-Step.3

As described above, the final step of our approach is to manually check the data samples in *M_Group*. For each code smell, the manual verification process encompasses two important tasks. First, the developer determines whether a given data sample is a smelly software entity. To support accurate annotation, we supply explicit refactoring guidelines for each code smell, thereby promoting both efficiency and consistency in the annotation process. Second, if the software entity is identified as smelly, the developer specifies the appropriate refactoring

action. For instance, which lines should be extracted from a long method, which methods should be extracted from a large class, or to which related target class a feature envy method should be moved. Detailed guidelines for each code smell are provided as follows.

For long method, developers will mark the data samples according to the following guidelines.

1. Is the target method hard to read?
2. Is the target method accessing too many attributes or other methods that may reduce the maintainability of the software?
3. Does the target method have multiple functions or too many parameters, which may reduce the reusability of the method?
4. If the target method is a long method, which lines should be extracted from this method.

For large class, developers will mark the data sample according to the following guidelines

1. Does the class have too many lines of code?
2. Does the class have too many fields?
3. Does the class have too many complex methods?
4. Does the class have class extraction opportunities that may reduce the reusability of the target class?
5. Does the class have too many responsibilities, which may reduce the maintainability of the target class?
6. If the target class is a large class, which method should be extracted from the target class.

For feature envy, developers will mark the data sample according to the following guidelines.

1. Does the method frequently call from another class?
2. Does the method frequently access another class?
3. Does the method rarely use attributes in its own class?
4. Does the method seem more cohesive with another class semantically?
5. If the target method is identified as feature envy, which class should it be moved to?

The annotation process was supported by a custom annotation tool developed in this study. An earlier version of this tool was introduced in our previous work [11]. In this study, we have extended its functionality by implementing a JetBrains plugin. This updated version allows developers to annotate data samples more efficiently within the IDE, thereby facilitating large-scale code smell data annotation through remote collaboration. The tool is publicly available at: https://github.com/Bankzhy/sce_exp.git.

4 Graph Construction

To enable the application of GNNs to code smell refactoring, it is necessary to transform the source code into a graph representation. In our approach, we designed a novel dual-level heterogeneous graph (DHG), which integrates both class-level and method-level representations. The class-level graph consists of a class node, method nodes, and the relationships among them. The method-level graph is composed of a method node, statement nodes, and their corresponding relationships. Node features were derived from a set of software metrics. The details of feature computation are described in Section 4.1, while the construction of the class-level and method-level graphs is explained in Sections 4.2 and 4.3, respectively.

4.1 Metrics Calculation

Software metrics are widely recognized as fundamental techniques for software quality assessment. In this study, these metrics were incorporated as node features within the input graph, providing a quantitative representation of structural and behavioral characteristics of software entities. The specific software metrics employed as node features are summarized in Table 8.

Table 8 Software metrics used in graph construction

Metrics	Level	Description
NOM [4]	Class	Number of Methods.
NOA [4]	Class	Number of Attributes.
NOPA [4]	Class	Number of public attributes.
ATFD [4]	Class	Access to foreign data
WMC [4]	Class	Weighted method count
TCC [4]	Class	Tight class cohesion
CIS [26]	Class	Class interface size
DCC [26]	Class	Direct class coupling
CAM [26]	Class	Cohesion among methods of class
DIT [17]	Class	Depth of inheritance tree
LCOM [17]	Class	Lack of Cohesion in Methods
LOC [10]	Method	Lines of Code
CC [10]	Method	McCabe's Cyclomatic Complexity
PC [10]	Method	Parameter Count
LCOM1-4 [15]	Method	Lack of Cohesion in Methods
NOAV [4]	Method	Number of accessed variables
TSMC	Method	Method text similarity with class
NFDI	Method	Number of Foreign data invocation
NLDI	Method	Number of Local data invocation
ABCL [16]	Statement	Type of statement (assign, branch, condition or loop)
FUC [10]	Method/Statement	Total number of fields used in one method / statement.
LMUC [10]	Method/Statement	Total used of local methods / fields.
VUC [10]	Statement	Total number of variables.
PUC [10]	Statement	Total number of parameters.
NBD [10]	Method/Statement	Nesting depth of the current statement.
WC [10]	Statement	Word count of the statement.
TSM	Statement	Statement text similarity with Method

4.2 Class Level Graph Construction

At the class level, the graph construction largely follows the methodology established in our previous study [11]. For clarity, we briefly illustrate the construction process using the example code shown in Figure 5.

FIGURE 5 The example code of class level graph

To construct the input graph for the example class, we first calculate the similarity matrix proposed by Akash [21], which incorporates three key metrics: *SSM*, *CDM*, and *CSM*. Based on this similarity matrix, the class-level graph is then constructed as illustrated in Figure 6. To improve readability, the graph is presented with distinct edge types. The input graph consists of two types of nodes (class nodes and method nodes) representing the target class and its methods, respectively. It also includes four types of edges: three types of method-to-method edges (*SSM*, *CDM*, and *CSM*) derived from the similarity matrix, and one *Include* edge linking the class node to all method nodes within the class. Further details on the calculation of node and edge attributes can be found in our previous study [11].

FIGURE 6 The example of class level input graph

4.3 Method Level Graph Construction

At the method level, the graph is constructed following the approach presented in our previous study [10]. For clarity, we use the example program in Figure 7, which implements an insertion sort algorithm in Java, to briefly explain the construction of method-level input graph. The method-level input graph extends the Program Dependence Graph (PDG) [18] and comprises two types of nodes (*Method Nodes* and *Statement Nodes*) and four types of edges: *Include*, *Control Flow*, *Control Dependency*, and *Data Dependency*. *Method Nodes* and *Statement Nodes* represent the target method and its constituent statements, respectively. The *Include* edge captures the relationship between a Method Node and its Statement Nodes, while the other three edge types model the relationships among statements. Detailed procedures for constructing this graph are provided in our previous study [10].

FIGURE 7 The example of method level input graph

5 Code Smell Refactoring using GNNs

In this section, we describe the application of GNNs to code smell refactoring. Detailed methodologies for each type of code smell are provided in Subsections 5.1 through 5.3.

5.1 Long Method Refactoring using GNNs

There are two important tasks in long method refactoring: long method detection and the identification of extract method opportunities. We take these two tasks as two types of training processes: graph classification and node classification.

In the long method detection, we take it as a graph classification task, the entire method-level input graph is fed into the GNN to identify if the method is a smelly method or not. We utilize eight metrics as the node feature for both method node and statement node. The method node features including: LOC, CC, PC, LCOM1-4, NOAV, and the statement node features including: ABCL, FUM, LMUC, PUC, NBD, VUC, WC, TSMM. The details of this step have also been explained in our previous study [10].

Next, in this study, we further extend GNN-based approach to find the extract method opportunities. Specifically, all statement nodes in the method-level input graph are passed to the GNN for node classification, where the goal is to determine whether a given statement should be extracted from the target method. Furthermore, to preserve the logical integrity of code blocks, we split the method into several blocks with the approach proposed by Silva [19][20]. Each block is then iteratively examined, and if more than 50% of the statement nodes within a block are classified as positive, the block is marked as an extraction opportunity.

5.2 Large Class Refactoring using GNNs

In large class refactoring, there are also two important tasks: large class detection and the identification of extract class opportunities. Similar to the long method refactoring process, these tasks could be also taken as graph classification and node classification, respectively.

For large class detection, we take the problem as a graph classification task. Specifically, the entire class-level input graph is fed into the GNN to determine whether the class is smelly or not. In this process, twelve software metrics are employed as node features for both class node and method node. The class node features including: NOM, NOA, NOPA, CIS, ATFD, WMC, TCC, DCC, LCOM, CAM, DIT, and NOAM. The method node features including: LOC, CC, PC, LCOM1-3, TSMC, NBD, FUC, LMUC, NOAV, and NBD. The detailed procedure of this step has been thoroughly described in our previous study [11].

Next, we extend the GNN-based approach to identify extract class opportunities. Specifically, all method nodes in the class-level input graph are put into the GNN for node classification, to determine whether a method should be extracted from the class. Methods that are classified as positive are marked as extract class opportunities.

5.3 Feature Envy Refactoring using GNNs

In feature envy refactoring, the first step is to identify the related classes of the target method. The related classes include all classes referenced within the method, such as parameter classes, attribute classes, and variable classes, consistent with the definition of related classes in Section 3.2.

Next, feature envy identification is conducted for the target method and each of its related classes. The class-level input graph corresponding to the target method is processed by the GNN to perform node classification, aiming to determine whether the method should be labeled as feature envy. Different from the extract class opportunities task, this step incorporates two additional distance metrics specifically designed for feature envy, as defined in Eq. (5) and (6). These distance-based metrics are integrated into the node features to enhance the

capability of the GNN in detecting smelly methods. Similar distance measures have also been employed in existing studies [5][6][14] to support feature envy detection.

$$SOURCE\ DIST = 1 - \frac{S_m \cap S_C}{S_m \cup S_C}, \text{ where } S_C = \bigcup_{e_i \in C} \{e_i\} \quad (5)$$

$$TARGET\ DIST = 1 - \frac{S_m \cap S'_C}{S_m \cup S'_C}, \text{ where } S'_C = S_C / \{m\} \quad (6)$$

The computed distance values are incorporated as method node features in the class-level input graph, which is then fed into the GNN for node classification to detect feature envy. The class node features including: LOC, NOM, NOA, NOPA, CIS, ATFD, WMC, TCC, DCC, LCOM, CAM, DIT, and NOAM. The method node features including: CC, PC, LCOM1-3, TSMC, NBD, FUC, LMUC, NOAV, SOURCE DIST, and TARGET DIST. If a method is classified as positive, it is considered to exhibit feature envy, and the corresponding related class is suggested as the target class for refactoring.

6 Evaluation Experiment

Based on the above ideas, we made the experiment to evaluate the performance of proposed approach. In section 6.1, we will elaborate on the basic information of the experiment. Next, the evaluation experiment details will be explained from Section 6.2 to Section 6.4.

6.1 Experiment Design

In our experiments, we focus on implementation and evaluation at four main parts. First, a new code smell refactoring dataset will be created based on the semi-automated dataset generation approach described in Section 3. The dataset includes three types of code smells: long method, large class, and feature envy, which could be utilized for both training and evaluation in code smell related tasks.

Next, we conducted experiments on long method detection and the identification of extract method opportunities using the above dataset. Three typical GNN model architectures were applied and compared against existing approaches. Specifically, for the long method detection task, our models were evaluated in comparison with JDeodorant, a classical metrics-based approach, and Liu’s approach, a representative deep learning-based approach. For the extract method opportunities identification task, however, only JDeodorant was used as a baseline, since Liu’s proposed approach addresses solely the long method detection task.

Subsequently, the experiments on large class were conducted in a similar process. including the detection of large class instances and the identification of extract class opportunities. The experimental procedures and evaluation were consistent with those described for the long method experiments.

Finally, we performed the experiment on feature envy. In this task, the detection process first finding the related classes of the target method and then to identify whether the method smelly or not with target class. Therefore, only one type of experiment was needed: identifying whether a method is a feature envy. Also, as in the previous tasks, we compared the results with the two baseline approaches described above.

Each above experiment will be evaluated and analyzed in the following subsections.

6.1.1 Experiment Setup

In this section, we present the supporting techniques and implementation used in our experiments. First, in dataset generation, we primarily used the Python language and ‘tree-sitter’ [43] to develop the assist tools for data sample generation and classification. In addition, we built an annotation tool based on the JetBrains Plugin development framework, which has

been released at the following link: <https://plugins.jetbrains.com/plugin/27007-sce-exp>. All manual annotation tasks in this study were conducted using this tool.

In our experiment, we applied three typical GNN model architectures to code smell refactoring: GCN [23], GraphSage [24] and GAT [25]. Each of these three model architectures has unique characteristics. In brief, GCN is a basic GNN model that obtains node feature information from itself and all neighboring nodes. GraphSage acquires node representation by aggregating information from neighbor sampling. GAT uses an attention mechanism to learn the weights from different nodes.

FIGURE 8 The model architecture of GNN models

All three GNN models were constructed according to the architecture in Figure 13. The network consists of two GNN layers and one linear layer. In addition, Adam was used as the optimizer, and cross-entropy was used as the loss function. The experiments relied on the PyTorch [44], whereas the implementation of the GNN predominantly utilized DGL [45].

6.1.2 Evaluation Criteria

In our experiment, we utilized three common metrics to evaluate the refactoring performance of the proposed approach: precision, recall, and F1. Precision is the ratio of positive samples marked by developers to detected positive samples. Recall is the probability of being predicted as a positive sample for all classes labeled as positive by developers. F1 is the harmonized average of the above two metrics, and it is calculated using Eq. (5).

$$F1 = \frac{2 \times Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (5)$$

6.1.3 Evaluation Questions

In the evaluation, we aim to verify the effectiveness of the proposed approach and determine whether its performance is superior to that of existing approaches. The mainly focused research questions are listed below.

Q1. How does the detection performance of the proposed approach compare with those of existing long method detection approaches?

Q2. How does the extract method opportunities identification performance of the proposed approach compare with those of existing extract method opportunities identification approaches?

Q3. How does the detection performance of the proposed approach compare with those of existing large class detection approaches?

Q4. How does the extract class opportunities identification performance of the proposed approach compare with those of existing extract class opportunities identification approaches?

Q5. How does the feature envy identification performance of the proposed approach compare with those of existing feature envy identification approaches?

6.2 Experiment Dataset

To support the experiment process, we first created a large-scale code smell refactoring dataset. We collected 16 open-source java projects as the code corpus including: JEdit [27], RxJava [28], Junit4 [29], Mybatis3 [30], Netty [31], Gephi [32], Plantuml [33], Groot [34], MusicBot [35], Traccar [36], JgraphT [37], Libgdx [38], Freeplane [39], Jsprit [40], Open Hospital [41], and OpenRefine [42]. We applied semi-automatic generation techniques to the first ten projects as training datasets, while using the remaining six projects as evaluation datasets, mainly based on manual data annotation. The whole dataset including over 13,000 positive data samples and over 70,000 negative data samples. The overview of this dataset is shown in Table 9, and it has been released in https://github.com/Bankzhy/GCSM_Dataset.git.

Table 9 Dataset overview

	Long Method	Large Class	Feature Envy
Positive	5,120	3,376	4,726
Negative	49,991	9,722	12,578
Total	55,111	13,098	17,304

For the training dataset, we applied the semi-automated generation technique introduced in Section 3. In the process of data sample automatic generation and grouping, it was supported by an assist program implemented by us. The program first transforms all target projects to the abstract syntax tree (AST) using the “tree-sitter” [43], then generates the merged class and divides it into two groups, following the rules in Section 3.3. Next, in manually checking phase, it was achieved by three Java developers. Finally, we got the training dataset with totally over 20,000 data samples. The detailed proportion of the training dataset is shown in Table 10. For the evaluation dataset, we applied manually checking phase for all classes and methods.

Table 10 Training dataset overview

	Long Method	Large Class	Feature Envy
Positive	4,298	3,119	4,253
Negative	4,298	3,119	4,253
Total	8,596	6,238	8,506

In the manually checking phase, we employed three Java developers, each with over eight years of Java program experience. It was supported by the annotation tool developed by us which we mentioned in Section 6.1.1. As results, the evaluation dataset consisted of over 20,000 data samples, and the proportion of the evaluation dataset is shown in Table 11.

Table 11 Evaluation dataset overview

	Long Method	Large Class	Feature Envy
Positive	822	257	473
Negative	13,596	3,197	3,783
Total	14,418	3,454	4,256

6.3 Evaluation for Long Method

In this subsection, we performed the experiment on long method following the process in Section 5.1. As we mentioned in previous sections, we perform two training tasks, the graph classification task for long method detection and the node classification task for extract method identification. We applied three GNN model architectures to each of task and compared results with existing approaches. The evaluation dataset we used for long method including four projects: Open Hospital, Libgdx, Jsprit, OpenRefine. The experiment results are shown in Figure 9 and Table 9. We will explain the results focusing on the research questions Q1 and Q2 as follows.

Q1. How does the detection performance of the proposed approach compare with those of existing long method detection approaches?

FIGURE 9 Long method detection results

From Figure 9, it could be observed that for the long method detection task, deep learning-based approaches significantly outperform traditional metrics-based approach across all evaluation metrics. Compared with Liu's deep learning approach, our graph-based deep learning approach achieved better performance in both precision and F1 score. Among them, GraphSAGE and GAT showed slightly better than GCN. These results are generally consistent with the findings of our earlier small-scale evaluation experiments [10].

Q2. How does the extract method opportunities identification performance of the proposed approach compare with those of existing extract method opportunities identification approaches?

For extract method opportunities identification, we evaluated each approach by identifying which lines should be extracted from the smelly methods. When constructing the evaluation dataset, we have asked the developers to annotate the specific lines of code that should be extracted into a new method. Based on the developers' annotations, we calculated the average metrics of each approach, as summarized in Table 12. From Table 12, it could be observed that the proposed graph-based deep learning approach outperforms existing refactoring tools in terms of both precision and recall, demonstrating the high effectiveness of the proposed approach.

Table 12 Extract method refactoring results

Approach	Average Precision	Average Recall	Average F1
GCN	0.5	0.56	0.53
GraphSage	0.51	0.62	0.56
GAT	0.51	0.62	0.56
JDeodorant	0.43	0.42	0.42

6.4 Evaluation for Large Class

In this subsection, we will explain the experiment results on large class refactoring. As we mentioned in previous sections, we performed two training tasks, the graph classification task for large class detection and the node classification task for extract class opportunities identification. We applied three GNN model architectures to each of tasks and compared results with existing approaches. The evaluation dataset we used for large class including six projects: Jgrapht, Libgdx, Freeplane, Jsprit, Open Hospital, and OpenRefine. The experiment results are shown in Figure 10 and Table 13. We will introduce the experiment results focusing on the research questions Q3 and Q4.

Table 13 Extract class refactoring results

Approach	Average Precision	Average Recall	Average F1
GCN	0.41	0.72	0.52
GraphSage	0.42	0.96	0.58
GAT	0.43	0.72	0.54
JDeodorant	0.44	0.22	0.29

Q3. How does the detection performance of the proposed approach compare with those of existing large class detection approaches?

FIGURE 10 Large class detection results

From Figure 10, it could be observed that deep learning-based approaches consistently

outperform the traditional approach JDeodorant across all metrics. Liu’s approach achieved the highest recall of 0.83, while our proposed graph-based deep learning approaches outperformed others in terms of precision and F1 score. However, no significant differences were observed among the three GNN architectures, with GAT showing a slightly higher F1 score than the others.

Q4. How does the extract class opportunities identification performance of the proposed approach compare with those of existing extract class opportunities identification approaches?

For extract class opportunities identification, we will evaluate each approach by identifying which methods should be extracted from the smelly class. When constructing the evaluation dataset, we have asked the developers to annotate the specific methods that should be extracted into a new class. Based on the developers’ annotations, we calculated the average metrics of each approach, as summarized in Table 13. From Table 13, it could be observed that the proposed graph-based deep learning approach outperforms existing refactoring approach in terms of both precision and recall, demonstrating the high effectiveness of the proposed approach.

6.5 Evaluation for Feature Envy

In this section, we performed evaluation experiment on feature envy. During the refactoring process, we first identify the related classes of each target method using the approach described in Section 5.3. We then perform a classification task that incorporates the related class to determine whether the target method is smelly or not. Methods identified as smelly are treated as feature envy, and the related class will be used as the recommended refactoring targets. In the evaluation process, the evaluation dataset including: JGraphT, LibGDX, Freeplane, Jsprit, Open Hospital, and OpenRefine. We will evaluate all methods in the evaluation dataset and calculate their average metrics. The results are shown in Figure 11, and we will analyze them with respect to Q5.

Q5. How does the Feature Envy identification performance of the proposed approach compare with those of existing feature envy identification approaches?

FIGURE 11 Feature envy detection results

From Figure 11, it could be observed that deep learning-based approaches consistently outperform the traditional approach JDeodorant across all metrics. Liu’s approach achieved the highest recall of 0.83, while our graph-based deep learning approaches outperformed others in terms of precision and F1 score. However, no significant differences were observed among

the three GNN architectures, with GAT showing a slightly higher F1 score than the others.

However, we could also find that all approaches achieve relatively low performance in the feature envy refactoring task. The traditional approach JDeodorant performs better in terms of precision but shows poor recall. Deep learning-based approaches generally achieve higher recall, with our proposed graph-based deep learning approach, GraphSAGE, reaching the best recall of 0.84. In terms of F1 score, our approach generally achieves around 0.3, with GraphSAGE achieving the highest value of 0.32. These results confirm the effectiveness of our approach compared to existing methods.

There are several factors that may cause the above results. First, the proportion of feature envy instances in the code corpus is relatively low, which makes the training data heavily reliant on automatically generated data samples. In contrast, all samples in the evaluation dataset are annotated by developers, which may lead to some performance degradation. Second, during the construction of the evaluation dataset, developers may have different perspectives and criteria for identifying feature envy, sometimes considering the overall class structure of the project. In our approach, however, we construct the input graph only based on the class of the target method, which may also contribute to the observed performance loss.

7 Discussion

In this section, we discuss several factors that may affect the performance of the proposed approach.

The semi-automated dataset generation approach proposed in this study allows us to obtain large-scale high-quality data samples with relatively low manual effort. We acknowledge, however, that a small number of erroneous samples may exist among the automatically generated data, since the grouping rules in Section 3.3 cannot be always useful for all data samples. Nevertheless, since we established the possibility-range and conducted extensive investigations for threshold setting, the proposed data generation approach could still be considered trustworthy. On the other hand, part of the dataset was manually annotated by three developers. Although we provided detailed guidelines for the annotation task, differences in individual judgment were inevitable for some ambiguous data samples. Cross-validation among annotators could mitigate this issue, but such a process would require a significant time investment, which we did not adopt at this stage. Moreover, the main advantage of deep learning lies in its ability to tolerate minor imperfections in the data when trained on a sufficiently large dataset, which makes this generation approach highly effective in practice.

The graph-based deep learning approach proposed in this study applies both class-level and method-level graphs to address the refactoring of three types of code smells. Although the experiments have demonstrated the effectiveness of our approach, we acknowledge that for certain code smells such as feature envy, it is necessary to consider the overall class structure of the project to make more accurate judgments. In future work, we would extend the levels of graphs to further enhance the generalizability and performance of the proposed approach.

8 Conclusion

In this study, we proposed a graph deep learning approach for code smell refactoring using GNNs. We designed the input graph at two representation levels (class level and method level) and employed both graph classification and node classification tasks to address the refactoring of three representative code smells: long method, large class, and feature envy. To get substantial training data samples, we proposed a semi-automatic dataset generation approach and the assist labeling tool to get the training and evaluation datasets each containing over 20,000 samples. In our experiment, we implemented proposed approach in three typical GNN model architectures and compared the results with existing code smell refactoring approaches. Experimental results demonstrate that our approach achieved promising performance across all three code smells.

In future work, we aim to extend this study in several directions. First, we plan to further prove the generalizability of the proposed approach by applying the proposed approach to additional code smells, such as shotgun surgery and divergent change. Second, we will investigate multi-level code smell refactoring, enabling the approach to provide more precise and context-aware refactoring suggestions. Finally, we intend to implement the approach as a practical tool to assist developers in performing code refactoring more efficiently.

References

- [1] Fowler M, Beck K, Brant J, Opdyke W. Refactoring: Improving the Design of Existing Code. USA; 1999.
- [2] AbuHassan A, Alshayeb M, Ghouti L. Software smell detection techniques: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Software: Evolution and Process*. 2021; 33:e2320.
- [3] Sharma T, Spinellis D. A survey on software smells. *Journal of Systems and Software* 2018; 138:158–173.
- [4] Lanza M and Marinescu R. *Object-Oriented Metrics in Practice*. Berlin: Springer; 2006.
- [5] Tsantalis N, Chatzigeorgiou A. Identification of extract method refactoring opportunities for the decomposition of methods. *Journal of Systems and Software* 2011; 84:1757-1782.
- [6] Tsantalis N, Chatzigeorgiou A. Identification of Extract Method Refactoring Opportunities. *Process European Conference on Software Maintenance and Reengineering* 2009; 119-128.
- [7] JDeodorant. <https://github.com/tsantalis/JDeodorant> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [8] Shahidi M, Ashtiani M, Zakeri-Nasrabadi M. An automated extract method refactoring approach to correct the long method code smell. *Journal of Systems and Software* 2022; 187:111221.
- [9] Fontana F A, Mäntylä M V, Zanoni M, Marino A. Comparing and experimenting machine learning techniques for code smell detection. *Empirical Software Engineering* 2016; 21:1143-1191.
- [10] Zhang HY, Kishi T. Long Method Detection Using Graph Convolutional Networks. *Journal of Information Processing* 2023; 31:469-477.
- [11] Zhang HY, Kishi T. Large Class Detection Using GNNs: A Graph Based Deep Learning Approach Utilizing Three Typical GNN Model Architectures. *IEICE Transactions on Information and Systems* 2024; E107.D:1140-1150.
- [12] Gori M, Monfardini G, Scarselli F. A new model for learning in graph domains. *IEEE International Joint Conference on Neural Networks* 2005; 2:729-734.
- [13] Scarselli F, Gori M, Hagenbuchner M, Monfardini G. The graph neural network model. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks* 2009; 20:61–80.
- [14] Liu H, Jin J, Xu Z, Zou Y, Bu Y, Zhang L. Deep Learning Based Code Smell Detection. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering* 2021; 47:1811-1837.
- [15] Charalampidou S, Ampatzoglou A, Avgeriou P. Size and cohesion metrics as indicators of the long method bad smell: An empirical study. In *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Predictive Models and Data Analytics in Software Engineering* 2015; 8:168-176.
- [16] Fitzpatrick J. Applying the ABC metric to C, C++, and Java, *Proc. More C++ Gems*. Cambridge University Press 2000:245-264.
- [17] Chidamber S.R., Kemerer C.F., A metrics suite for object oriented design. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering* 1994; 20:476-493.
- [18] Ferrante J, Ottenstein K J., Warren J D. The program dependence graph and its use in optimization. *ACM Transactions on Programming Languages and Systems* 1987; 9:319-349.
- [19] Silva D, Terra R, Valente M T. Recommending automated extract method refactorings. In *Proceedings of the 22nd International Conference on Program Comprehension* 2014; 146-156.
- [20] Silva D, Terra R, Valente M T. Jextract: an eclipse plugin for recommending automated extract method refactorings. *arXiv:1506.06086* 2015. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1506.06086>
- [21] Akash P, Sadiq A, Kabir A. An Approach of Extracting God Class Exploiting Both Structural and Semantic Similarity. In *Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Evaluation of Novel Approaches to Software Engineering (ENASE)* 2019; 427–433.

- [22] Zhou J, Cui G, Hu S, Zhang Z, Yang C, Liu Z, Wang L, Li C, Sun M. Graph neural networks: A review of methods and applications. *AI Open* 2020; 1:57-81.
- [23] Kipf T N, Welling M. Semi-supervised classification with graph convolutional networks. *ICLR* 2017.
- [24] Hamilton W L, Ying R, Leskovec J. Inductive representation learning on large graphs. *NIPS* 2017; 1024-1034.
- [25] Veličković P, Cucurull G, Casanova A, Romero A, Liò P, Bengio Y. Graph Attention Networks. *ICLR* 2018.
- [26] Bansiya J, Davis C G. A hierarchical model for object-oriented design quality assessment. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering* 2002; 28:4-17.
- [27] JEdit. <http://jedit.org/> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [28] RxJava. <https://github.com/ReactiveX/RxJava> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [29] Junit4. <https://github.com/junit-team/junit4> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [30] Mybatis3. <https://github.com/mybatis/mybatis-3> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [31] Netty. <https://github.com/netty/netty> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [32] Gephi. <https://github.com/gephi/gephi> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [33] Plantuml. <https://github.com/plantuml/plantuml> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [34] Groot. <https://github.com/gavalian/groot> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [35] MusicBot. <https://github.com/jagrosh/MusicBot> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [36] Traccar. <https://github.com/traccar/traccar> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [37] Jgrapht. <https://jgrapht.org> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [38] Libgdx. <https://github.com/libgdx/libgdx> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [39] Freeplane. <https://github.com/freeplane/freeplane> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [40] Jsprit. <https://github.com/graphhopper/jsprit> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [41] Open Hospital. <https://github.com/informatici/openhospital> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [42] OpenRefine. <https://github.com/OpenRefine/OpenRefine> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [43] tree-sitter. <https://github.com/tree-sitter/tree-sitter/> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [44] PyTorch, <https://pytorch.org/> (accessed 2025-04-29).
- [45] DGL, <https://www.dgl.ai/> (accessed 2025-04-29).